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Review Article

Goniothalamus Sesquipedalis: Ethnomedicine To Natural Pharmaceutical

Ajoykumar Thongbam*¹, Jayantakumar Thongbam²

¹Amity Institute of Biotechnology, Amity University, Noida - 201303

²Department of Botany, G.P. Women's College, Old Lambulane, Jail Road, Imphal - 795001

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ABSTRACT

Goniothalamus sesquipedalis, a rare species within the Annonaceae family, has garnered significant attention for its traditional medicinal uses and bioactive compounds. This plant is native to tropical Southeast Asia and is widely recognized for its efficacy in treating ailments such as fever, diarrhea, and body pains. Phytochemical screening has identified a range of compounds including alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, and sterols, which contribute to its medicinal properties. Bioactivity assays have demonstrated the plant's antibacterial, antioxidant, and analgesic activities, making it a potential source of natural pharmaceutical agents. Ethnomedicinal studies have highlighted the plant's cultural and health-related significance in traditional practices, particularly in Manipur, India, where it is used in various forms, including decoctions and steams, to treat various ailments. Despite its promising results, further research is needed to fully understand the plant's bioactive compounds, molecular mechanisms, and in vivo performance. This review aims to integrate available data, discuss conflicts of interest, and identify areas of further research to better utilize this plant's potential in traditional and modern medicine.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Goniothalamus*, part of the Annonaceae family, encompasses around 160 species [1,2]. This diverse genus thrives in the lowland and submontane forests of tropical Southeast Asia, particularly in Western Malesia, Sumatra, and Peninsular Malaysia, showcasing a remarkable adaptability to various environments [3–5]. In

India alone, over 10 species of *Goniothalamus* demonstrate the genus' extensive habitat range [6]. The medicinal potential of these plants is noteworthy, with some species traditionally used for ailments such as body pains, fever, and rheumatism, and for their anti-aging and abortifacient properties [6,7]. The bioactive compounds in these plants, including acetogenins,

*Corresponding Author: Ajoykumar Thongbam

Address: Amity Institute of Biotechnology, Amity University, Noida - 201303

Email ✉: ajthongbam@gmail.com

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styryl-lactones, and alkaloids, have shown cytotoxic and antimicrobial properties, reinforcing their use in traditional Asian medicine for cancer and infection treatments [8–12]. *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* stands out for its notable use in traditional medicinal practices in Manipur, India. It is utilized in various forms, such as decoctions and steams from medicinal concoctions, particularly for its efficacy in treating ailments like fever and diarrhea [13]. This usage underscores its importance in community health management across several districts in Manipur, where it also serves as an analgesic and even plays roles in rituals, showcasing its broad application spectrum [14,15]. And, goniothalamine, a staple compound in many *Goniothalamus* species has been noted for its anticancer, antioxidant, and anti-viral properties [16–18]. A very rare species amongst these studies is *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* which, despite a few preliminary screenings and assays [19,20], has not been as extensively examined in terms of identifying its bioactive compounds through mass spectrometry or other techniques of higher sensitivity, their molecular mechanisms of bioactive compounds through molecular docking and in vivo performance through animal models and so on. However, the results from these existing studies are very promising. Its methanol extract was first studied for its importance in traditional medicine in North East India and then, further proved to be a potential source of antibacterial agents [20]. Phytochemical screening of both the methanol and ethanol extracts revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, phlobatannin, glycosides, and sterols in its seeds, highlighting its potential as an analgesic agent [19,20]. Traditions corroborate such findings, it has been used as an analgesic, and its methanolic extracts have shown antibacterial effects, particularly against *E. coli* in places where it's available [21]. Essential oils from various *Goniothalamus* species, containing

sesquiterpenoids and monoterpenoids, contribute to their aromatic and medicinal attributes [20]. Meanwhile, Compounds isolated from related *Goniothalamus* species, such as goniotriol and pinocembrin, have demonstrated anti-HIV-1 RT inhibition and cytotoxic activities against different cell lines, indicating potential therapeutic benefits [9,22]. The exploration into the phylogenetics of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* has provided further insights into its evolutionary context within the Annonaceae family. Studies such as those by Tang et al. (2013) and, within a bioproject, have employed nuclear gene sequencing to elaborate on the phylogenetic relationships and diversification among Annonaceae members [4,23,24]. This phylogenetic framework helps in understanding the genetic lineage and potential adaptive traits of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis*, offering a broader evolutionary perspective that supports its pharmacological research [23,24]. Although not a large collection, some compounds have been identified from *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis*, research has shown the isolation of specific bioactive compounds like Goniopedaline and Aristololactam A-II from the plant [22,25,26]. These compounds have been analyzed for their pharmacological properties, emphasizing their potential therapeutic benefits, particularly in anticancer and antimicrobial activities. The ADMET properties of these compounds were specifically reviewed, revealing challenges such as low solubility and high plasma protein binding that could affect their therapeutic applications [27,28]. Therefore, in the interest of highlighting a potential, natural pharmaceutical agent in this rare species, this review will compare and integrate available data as a potential pharmaceutical agent, discuss conflicts of interest in the pursuit of studying this species, briefly call back to the use of *Goniothalamus* species, including *G. sesquipedalis*, in traditional medicine and most

importantly, point out missing information and areas of further research to be done.

A BRIEF HISTORY OF GONIOTHALAMUS SESQUIPEDALIS IN ETHNOMEDICINAL USE:

Ethnomedicine, passed down through generations via knowledge, skills, and beliefs, is widely used by tribal, non-tribal, and rural populations who rely on ethnoflora for various treatments [29–31]. Ethnobotanical studies provide valuable insights into these traditional medicinal practices [29]. In all countries around the world, over time, these practices evolved into codified systems like Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani, and Sowa-Rigpa [32–35]. In the realm of ethnomedicine, *Goniothalamus* is present throughout. For instance, *Goniothalamus* was among 71 different plants used for ethnomedicine in Tonga [36]. And, in Asia, *Goniothalamus* species are widely recognized for their medicinal uses across the southeast countries [37]. *Goniothalamus macrophyllus* is traditionally used in Malaysia and Indonesia as a fever remedy and general health tonic [37–39]. In the Bukit Pembarisan forest, West Java, *G. macrophyllus* is highly valued by local communities, with its population structure influenced by factors like soil nitrogen and pH [38]. In the Philippines, *Goniothalamus amuyon* is valued for its anti-inflammatory properties and its utility in treating various skin conditions [22]. In Thailand, other *Goniothalamus* species like *G. roseipetalus*, *G. sukhirinensis*, and *G. macrophyllus* are highlighted for their traditional, medicinal significance in pain relief and infection treatment [40]. *Goniothalamus giganteus*, used in Vietnam, is known for treating

digestive issues and stomach aches, highlighting its significance in traditional medicinal systems [22]. And, *Goniothalamus fulvus*, is similarly employed for its health benefits in various Southeast Asian countries [37]. There is numerous other instances of traditional usage of *Goniothalamus* species in ethnomedicine throughout the world and a more comprehensive and detailed account is given in an earlier review [6]. In a similar capacity, *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* has been integral to the traditional medicinal practices in the Indian north-eastern state of Manipur, showcasing a variety of uses proving its cultural and health-related importance throughout many districts of the state. Among the people of Senapati district, this plant is a key component of medicinal concoctions [13]. The steam from these concoctions is used to treat common ailments such as fever and diarrhea [13], reflecting the plant's role in community health management. In the Bishnupur district, specifically within the Chothe tribe, *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* serves multiple functions—not only as an insecticide and blood purifier but also in rituals to drive away spirits [14], indicating its deep-rooted significance in both the practical and spiritual lives of the community. Moreover, in the Thoubal district of Manipur, where the plant is sparsely distributed, it plays a unique role in neonatal care [15]. A decoction made from this plant is traditionally used as a bath for newborn children, which is believed to impart protective health benefits [15], safeguarding the well-being of the most vulnerable members of the society. An overview of the uses in Manipur is given Table 1.

Table 1: Ethnomedicinal Uses of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* in Manipur, India

District	Usage	Reference
Senapati	Used in medicinal concoctions; steam used for treating fever and diarrhea	Imotomba & Devi, 2011
Bishnupur	Used as an insecticide, blood purifier, and in rituals to drive away spirits	Sanglakpam et al., 2012

Thoubal	Decoction used as a bath for newborn children to impart protective health benefits	Sinam, 2007
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Adding to its medicinal repertoire, *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* is traditionally recognized for its analgesic properties as it is also widely used in traditional medicine across the different regions around Asia to alleviate pain, providing a natural alternative to synthetic pain relievers [19]. These diverse applications of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* in Manipur not only exemplify the plant's versatility in traditional medicine but also its enduring relevance in the healthcare practices of indigenous communities. This aligns with the broader patterns observed in other regions where *Goniothalamus* species are employed, reinforcing the global importance of ethnomedicine in contemporary health systems and the need for continued ethnobotanical research to preserve and understand these invaluable traditional knowledge systems.

OVERVIEW OF BIO-ACTIVITY STUDIES DONE WITH GONIOTHALAMUS SESQUIPEDALIS:

Research on *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* has progressively unveiled its diverse pharmacological properties, indicating its significant potential in both traditional and modern medicine. The exploration into the ethnomedicinal applications of this plant began with studies focused on its antibacterial properties. For instance, Kongsam et al. (2015) investigated the antibacterial activities of the plant's methanolic extracts against *Bacillus subtilis* and *Escherichia coli*, finding significant inhibition zones that confirmed its efficacy [20]. The study highlighted the presence of key phytochemicals such as alkaloids, flavonoids, and terpenoids, which contribute to its medicinal value [20]. However, the study was limited by its focus on only two bacterial strains, which may not fully represent the plant's antibacterial potential against a broader

spectrum of pathogens [20]. Building on the foundational antibacterial studies, Khan et al. (2018) performed a detailed phytochemical screening of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis*, identifying a wide range of active compounds including alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, and sterols [19]. This study provided a scientific basis for the plant's use as an analgesic agent in traditional medicine, further broadening our understanding of its bioactive components. However, the study's main drawback was its lack of *in vivo* testing, which is crucial for confirming the efficacy and safety of these phytochemicals in biological organisms [19]. The scope of research expanded further with the work of Rahman et al. (2019), who explored both the antimicrobial and antioxidant activities of the plant. Their study demonstrated that the ethanol extract of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* not only continued to show substantial antimicrobial activity against pathogens such as *E. coli* but also exhibited notable antioxidant capabilities, adding an additional layer of therapeutic potential [41]. Despite these findings, the study did not explore the mechanisms underlying these effects, which are essential for developing targeted therapies [42]. Most recently, Habiba et al. (2019) delved into the anthelmintic and insecticidal properties of the plant. Their research revealed significant dose-dependent anthelmintic activity against earthworms and high insecticidal activity against *Sitophilus oryzae*, showcasing the plant's versatility and broadening its range of potential applications beyond merely antibacterial and antioxidant uses. One limitation of this study, however, was its focus on a single insect species, which might not provide a complete picture of the plant's insecticidal range [43].

G. SESQUIPEDALIS EXHIBITS SIGNIFICANT ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY:

The antimicrobial activities of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* have been thoroughly explored through several studies, employing various methodologies and targeting different microbial strains. These investigations have focused primarily on antibacterial properties, with less emphasis or data available on antifungal effects.

Konsam et al. (2015) initiated a focused investigation into the antibacterial properties of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* using methanolic extracts. Employing the well-diffusion method, a common technique for assessing antimicrobial activity, the study measured the inhibition zones produced by the extracts against two bacterial strains: *Bacillus subtilis* and *Escherichia coli*. The well-diffusion method involves applying the extract to wells punched in agar plates pre-inoculated with the bacterial strains [41]. The effectiveness is evaluated by measuring the diameter of the inhibition zones formed around the wells, indicating the extent to which the bacterial growth has been hindered [44,45]. This method provides a visual and quantitative measure of antimicrobial potency. The study showed significant inhibitory effects against both bacterial strains [20], suggesting a broad spectrum of activity within the bacterial domain. However, it did not explore antifungal activity, leaving a gap in the understanding of the plant's efficacy against fungal pathogens [20]. Rahman (2019) extended the analysis of the antimicrobial properties of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* by using ethanol extracts and incorporating both the DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) assay for antioxidant activity and the well-diffusion method for antimicrobial testing [42]. This study also targeted *Escherichia coli*, using the same well-diffusion technique to assess the inhibition zones. Additionally, the antioxidant capabilities were

evaluated using the DPPH free radical scavenging assay, which, while primarily an assessment of antioxidant capacity, indirectly supports the therapeutic potential of the extracts, including potential synergistic effects on antimicrobial action. Like the previous study, Rahman (2019) focused solely on bacterial strains without incorporating fungal pathogens, which remains a notable omission in the broader context of antimicrobial research [42]. In summary, the antimicrobial investigations of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* have demonstrated significant antibacterial activity through well-established methods like the well-diffusion assay. To enhance the robustness and breadth of studies on the antimicrobial activity of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis*, future research could adopt several approaches. Firstly, expanding the spectrum of microbial strains tested, including a variety of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, along with fungal pathogens, would provide a more comprehensive assessment of the plant's antimicrobial capabilities [46]. Incorporating advanced techniques such as broth microdilution could offer more precise measurements of minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs), enhancing the quantitative analysis of antimicrobial potency [47]. Additionally, employing molecular techniques like mass spectrometry and NMR spectroscopy could help identify and characterize the active compounds [48–50], giving researchers a deeper understanding of the mechanisms underlying the antimicrobial effects. With the compounds identified by mass spectrometry and NMR spectroscopy, molecular docking would serve as a sophisticated computational technique that enhances the understanding of the antimicrobial properties of compounds found in *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* [51–55]. This method predicts how molecular ligands from the plant might interact with specific protein targets within microbial

pathogens, helping to estimate their binding affinities and potential efficacy [53,55]. A higher binding affinity indicated by docking can suggest a strong and effective interaction, potentially capable of inhibiting or altering the function of the target protein, which could result in the disruption of microbial pathogenicity and survival. The insights gained from molecular docking extend beyond simple interaction predictions. They can elucidate the mechanisms through which plant-derived compounds exert their antimicrobial effects, such as competitive inhibition—where the compound prevents the natural substrate from binding to the enzyme—or allosteric inhibition, where the compound binds to an alternative site on the protein, influencing the enzyme's activity indirectly [56,57]. These interactions can be visually analyzed through docking simulations, offering a detailed view of how plant compounds fit within the active sites of microbial proteins.

Additionally, molecular docking facilitates the optimization of bioactive compounds. By understanding how these molecules interact at a molecular level with target proteins, chemists can modify and optimize their structures to enhance binding characteristics, increase selectivity, reduce toxicity, and improve overall antimicrobial efficacy [58–62]. This approach is crucial for advancing plant-based compounds from preliminary screening stages to potential clinical applications. For practical applications in docking studies, certain microbial enzymes and proteins that are critical for pathogen survival and virulence can be targeted. Examples include DNA Gyrase (Bacterial Topoisomerase II), essential for bacterial DNA replication [63–65]; β -ketoacyl-ACP Synthase (FabB/FabF), involved in bacterial fatty acid synthesis [66–68]; Lanosterol 14 α -demethylase (CYP51), crucial in fungal ergosterol biosynthesis [69,70]; and Penicillin-Binding Proteins (PBPs), key components in bacterial cell wall synthesis [71–74]. Targeting these proteins

can potentially lead to the discovery of novel antimicrobial agents that are effective against resistant strains of bacteria and fungi. Moreover, synergistic studies examining the interaction of this plant's extracts with conventional antibiotics could uncover potential enhancements in efficacy, addressing issues of antibiotic resistance [75,76].

DISSATISFACTORY ASSESSMENT OF ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY:

The assessment of antioxidant activity in *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* has been specifically addressed in the studies by Rahman (2019), employing a distinct methodology to evaluate the plant's ability to mitigate oxidative stress [42]. Rahman's study comprehensively examined the antioxidant capabilities of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* using the DPPH assay [42]. The DPPH assay is a widely used method to measure the ability of antioxidants to scavenge free radicals, indicated by a change in color as the radical is reduced [77–80]. Rahman found that the ethanol extract of the plant demonstrated significant free radical scavenging activity. This finding suggests that the extract contains compounds capable of donating electrons to neutralize free radicals, thus providing a measure of the plant's potential antioxidant effects. However, the study conducted by Rahman (2019) on the antioxidant potential of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* provides is somewhat limited by the inherent nature of the DPPH assay employed. While the DPPH assay is popular for its straightforward methodology, which involves a simple colorimetric measurement of free radical scavenging activity, it only tests the capacity to neutralize one type of free radical. This specificity might lead to an incomplete assessment of the plant's overall antioxidant capabilities, as it does not account for other reactive species such as different types of oxygen or nitrogen radicals that are biologically relevant. Various studies have addressed this limitation by proposing alternative

methods to overcome interference from pigments in plant extracts [81,82] considering the spectroscopic properties of substances in the reaction medium [83], and developing modified assays to accurately measure antioxidant activity without underestimation or interference from coexisting pigments [82]. Moreover, the DPPH assay's outcomes can vary with factors like the solubility of the antioxidant, reaction time, and test conditions [84–86], which might influence the reproducibility and reliability of the results. Given these limitations, the findings from this single assay should be approached with caution, as they may not fully reflect the plant's antioxidant activity in biological systems. To enhance the understanding of the antioxidant properties of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis*, it is crucial to incorporate a broader range of assays in future research. For instance, the ABTS assay, which involves a similar radical scavenging mechanism but uses a different radical that is soluble in both water and organic solvents [84,87–89], could complement the DPPH results. Additionally, the Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) assay, which measures the ability of antioxidants to reduce ferric ions [90,91], could provide insight into the electron donation capacity of the plant's compounds. Other important tests include the Oxygen Radical Absorbance Capacity (ORAC) assay, which is relevant for evaluating the plant's effectiveness against biologically pertinent peroxy radicals [92,93], and metal chelation assays, which assess the ability to bind transition metals that catalyze radical formation [78,94,95]. Furthermore, conducting *in vivo* antioxidant tests could reveal the extract's impact on the oxidative status in biological systems, offering a more real-world appraisal of its therapeutic potential [77,96,97].

While the studies by Habiba et al. (2019), Konsam et al. (2015), and Khan et al. (2018) did not directly assess the antioxidant activity of *Goniothalamus*

sesquipedalis through specific assays, their findings have significant implications regarding the plant's potential antioxidant properties [19,20,43]. Konsam et al. and Khan et al. identified a variety of phytochemicals, including alkaloids, flavonoids, and tannins, known for their antioxidant capabilities [98–100]. These compounds can neutralize free radicals and may contribute to reducing oxidative stress in biological systems, suggesting possible health benefits such as anti-aging, anti-inflammatory, and anticarcinogenic effects [101–107]. These collective observations call for specific antioxidant testing in future studies to fully elucidate the therapeutic potential of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis*.

ANTHELMINTIC AND INSECTICIDAL ACTIVITIES:

The study by Habiba et al. (2019) focused extensively on exploring the anthelmintic and insecticidal activities of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis*, revealing significant biological effects that have implications for agricultural and pharmaceutical applications [43]. The research utilized a range of extracts from the plant, each prepared using different solvents to assess their efficacy against specific pests and parasites, specifically earthworms (*Pheretima posthuma*) for anthelmintic activity and rice weevils (*Sitophilus oryzae*) for insecticidal activity [43]. In their examination of anthelmintic activity, Habiba et al. utilized a bioassay with adult earthworms to test various concentrations of multiple extracts of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis*. [43] The study recorded the time to paralysis and death, noting a clear dose-dependent effectiveness, with higher concentrations leading to faster effects. Among the extracts, the ethanol extract was particularly noted for its potency, demonstrating strong anthelmintic properties by rapidly disrupting the biological functions of earthworms [43]. For insecticidal activity, the methodology involved treating rice

weevils (*Sitophilus oryzae*) with the same range of plant extracts and observing mortality rates over 24 hours. The results showed dose-dependent lethality, with higher concentrations resulting in higher mortality rates. These findings suggest potential applications in organic farming and natural pest control, positioning the extracts as eco-friendly alternatives to synthetic insecticides.

The study by Habiba et al. significantly contributes to the understanding of the potential uses of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* in pest and parasite control. The demonstrated anthelmintic and insecticidal activities suggest that extracts from this plant could be developed into natural remedies for controlling parasitic worms and agricultural pests. However, further research is necessary to isolate and identify the specific active compounds responsible for these effects, understand their mechanisms of action, and assess their safety and efficacy in real-world conditions. Additionally, expanding the scope of testing to include other pests and parasites could broaden the applicability of the findings.

PHYLOGENETIC EVALUATIONS:

The BioProject (NCBI Accession ID: PRJNA508895), involves multiple studies that explore the evolution and diversification of tropical rainforests at global scales. The project includes contributions from various studies, notably those by Couvreur T et al. (2019), which uses targeted enrichment of nuclear genes to understand the phylogenomics of the Annonaceae family, and by Bre B et al. (2020), which discusses the diversification of specific African rainforest-restricted clades within the family [23,24]. These explores the diversification of African rainforest-restricted clades within the Annonaceae family, revealing how historical biogeography and speciation events shaped their distribution and adaptation and uses targeted enrichment of nuclear genes to analyze the phylogenomics of the Annonaceae family,

providing a detailed framework for understanding the evolutionary relationships and genetic lineage of species like *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis*[23,24]. In another study primarily aimed to enhance the understanding of phylogenetic relationships within the Annonaceae family using advanced genomic techniques, specifically focusing on the targeted enrichment of nuclear genes to obtain a more resolved and accurate phylogeny [4]. This approach targeted specific genes believed to be crucial in evolutionary developments and adaptations across various species within the family. Methodologically, the Tang et al. (2013) employed a targeted enrichment approach, selecting particular segments of nuclear DNA for sequencing, which is especially useful in phylogenetics as it allows for the comparison of many genes across multiple species, providing a comprehensive genetic overview that is more informative than traditional single-gene studies [4]. By sequencing these targeted regions, high-resolution data were gathered to construct a detailed phylogenetic tree. Within this broader study, *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* was one of the species sampled for genetic data, and the sequences obtained helped place it accurately within the phylogenetic tree of the Annonaceae family [4]. The study identified several sequences from *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis*, specifically GenBank accession numbers KM818553, KM818612, KM818670, KM818712, KM818845, KM818929, KM818988, KM818781, and KM818744, which helped in accurately placing this species within the phylogenetic tree of the Annonaceae family [4]. *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis*, closely related to *Goniothalamus tapis* known for its anticancer and antimicrobial properties [108], and *Goniothalamus macrophyllus* with noted anti-inflammatory and anticancer effects [109], may similarly possess

valuable bioactive compounds, indicating significant pharmaceutical potential.

COMPOUNDS ISOLATED FROM GONIOTHALAMUS SESQUIPEDALIS ELUCIDATES BIOACTIVITY:

A small number of compounds isolated from *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* can be found from literature [22,25,26]. The isolated compounds from various parts of the plant highlight its diverse phytochemical profile. From the leaves and twigs, compounds such as Goniopedaline, aristololactam A-II, taliscanine, aurantiamide acetate, β -sitosterol, and β -d-glucoside have been isolated.

These substances are known for their bioactive properties, which can include antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and possibly anticancer effects. Additionally, from the stem bark, a distinct compound named 6S-(5-acetoxy)-7S, 8R-epoxystyryl-5,6-dihydro-2-pyrone (5-acetoxyisogoniothalamine oxide) has been extracted. This specific compound might offer unique biological activities, contributing further to the medicinal potential of the plant.

Some of these compounds are evaluated of their pharmacological properties using ADMET 2.0 [27,28].

Table 2: Pharmacological Properties of Compounds from *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis*

Compound Name	LogS	LogP	Human Intestinal Absorption (HIA)	Blood-Brain Barrier (BBB)	Plasma Protein Binding (PPB)
Goniopedaline	-6.03	3.62	1.6%	Low (0.065)	93.07%
Aristololactam A-II	-6.45	3.85	1.0%	Low (0.078)	94.72%
Aurantiamide acetate	-4.25	3.67	99.3%	Low (0.092)	95.93%

As given in Table 2, here are some of the most interesting parts of the analysis:

LogS (Solubility):

The negative LogS values indicate low solubility in water for all compounds [110], which might challenge their formulation for oral administration unless modifications or advanced delivery methods are employed.

LogP (Lipophilicity):

Values around 3.6-3.85 suggest that these compounds are moderately lipophilic [111,112], favoring absorption across cell membranes but might also indicate a risk of accumulating in fatty tissues.

Human Intestinal Absorption (HIA):

Except for Aurantiamide acetate, which shows almost complete absorption, the other compounds have very low absorption rates, potentially limiting their effectiveness when administered orally [113,114].

Blood-Brain Barrier (BBB):

All compounds have low permeability predictions regarding the blood-brain barrier, suggesting that they are less likely to affect central nervous system targets [115,116].

Plasma Protein Binding (PPB):

High binding rates (over 90%) indicate that these compounds, once in the bloodstream, are likely to bind significantly to plasma proteins, which could reduce their free concentration available for therapeutic action but might also prolong their systemic retention [117,118]. In simple terms, while these compounds show potential due to their lipophilic nature and in the case of Aurantiamide acetate, excellent intestinal absorption, their low water solubility and high plasma protein binding pose challenges for drug development. Strategies to enhance solubility and bioavailability will be crucial in harnessing their therapeutic potential.

CONCLUSION:

The comprehensive review of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* within the context of traditional and modern pharmacology underscores its significant

potential as a source of bioactive compounds. As detailed through various studies, this plant exhibits a broad spectrum of biological activities ranging from antimicrobial to analgesic properties [19,20]. The identification of specific compounds like Goniopedaline, Aristololactam A-II, and Aurantiamide acetate further validates the ethnomedicinal use of the plant, providing a scientific basis for its application in traditional medicine practices across various Asian communities [9,22]. Pharmacological evaluations, particularly those assessing ADMET properties, reveal challenges such as low solubility and high plasma protein binding, which could hinder the development of these compounds into therapeutic agents [27,28]. However, these challenges also open avenues for future research to optimize these compounds for better bioavailability. Additionally, the phylogenetic studies linking *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* to other species within the Annonaceae family highlight potential comparative paths to discover and harness similar bioactive profiles [4,23,24]. Despite the promising bioactivity profiles, the lack of extensive studies on this rare species, particularly those employing advanced molecular and in vivo methodologies, suggests a significant gap in the current scientific literature. This gap not only presents an opportunity for future research but also underscores the need for a concerted effort to explore this underutilized resource more comprehensively. Integrating advanced analytical techniques, such as mass spectrometry and molecular docking, with traditional ethnobotanical knowledge could yield new insights into the therapeutic potentials of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis*. In conclusion, *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* represents a reservoir of medicinal potential, aligned with both historical usage and modern pharmacological standards. Its continued study not only promises to expand our understanding of its bioactive compounds but also

contributes to the broader fields of ethnopharmacology and drug development, potentially leading to novel therapeutic agents that be able to take advantage of the unique properties of this relatively rare species.

REFERENCES:

1. Saunders R. A synopsis of *Goniothalamus* species (Annonaceae) in Peninsular Malaysia, with a description of a new species. *Bot J Linn Soc* 2003;142:321–39.
2. Wiart C. *Goniothalamus* Species: A Source of Drugs for the Treatment of Cancers and Bacterial Infections? *Evid-Based Complement Altern Med ECAM* 2007;4(3):299–311.
3. K.A. S, G Vadhyar R. A new species of *Goniothalamus* (Annonaceae) from the Western Ghats of Tamil Nadu, India. *Taiwania* 2020;65:176–80.
4. Tang CC, Xue B, Saunders RMK. A new species of *Goniothalamus* (Annonaceae) from Palawan, and a new nomenclatural combination in the genus from Fiji. *PhytoKeys* 2013;(32):27–35.
5. Venturina RE, Arriola A. *Goniothalamus luzonensis* (Annonaceae) a new species from Bataan, Luzon, Philippines. 2020;
6. Aslam M, Ahmad MS, Mamat A. *Goniothalamus*: Phytochemical and Ethnobotanical review. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci* 2015;
7. Jantan I, Ahmad F, Ahmad AS. A Comparative Study Of The Essential Oils Of Four *Goniothalamus* Species. *Acta Horti* 2005;(677):27–36.
8. Bihud NV, Rasol NE, Imran S, Awang K, Ahmad FB, Mai CW, et al. Goniolanceolatins A–H, Cytotoxic Bis-styryllactones from *Goniothalamus lanceolatus*. *J Nat Prod* 2019;82(9):2430–42.
9. Funnimid N, Pompimon W, Nuntasaeen N. In vitro Evaluation of Crude Extracts and

- Isolated Compounds from *Goniothalamus rongklanus* and *Goniothalamus latestigma* for Bioactive Properties. *J Nat Remedies* 2019;19(3):146–52.
10. Nguyen TK, Thi Tran LT, Truong Tan T, Pham PTV, Nguyen LTK, Nguyen HT, et al. Isolation, structural elucidation, and cytotoxic activity investigation of novel styryl-lactone derivatives from *Goniothalamus elegans*: in vitro and in silico studies. *RSC Adv* 2023;13(26):17587–94.
 11. Polbuppha I, Teerapongpisan P, Phukhatmuen P, Suthiphasilp V, Maneerat T, Charoensup R, et al. Alkaloids and Styryl lactones from *Goniothalamus ridleyi* King and Their α -Glucosidase Inhibitory Activity. *Molecules* 2023;28(3):1158.
 12. Teo SP, Bhakta S, Stapleton P, Gibbons S. Bioactive Compounds from the Bornean Endemic Plant *Goniothalamus longistipetes*. *Antibiotics* 2020;9(12):913.
 13. Imotomba R, Devi L. Creation of geo spatial data base of medicinal plants of Senapati district, Manipur. *Nat J Chem Biosis.* 2011;2(2):17-36. 2011;
 14. Sanglakpam P, Mathur RR, Pandey AK. Ethnobotany of Chothe tribe of Bishnupur district (Manipur). 2012;3:414–25.
 15. Sinam Y. Survey for Medicinal plants of Thoubal District. *Flora Fauna* 2007;
 16. Alabsi AM, Ali R, Ali AM, Harun H, Al-Dubai SAR, Ganasegeran K, et al. Induction of caspase-9, biochemical assessment and morphological changes caused by apoptosis in cancer cells treated with goniothalamine extracted from *Goniothalamus macrophyllus*. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev APJCP* 2013;14(11):6273–80.
 17. Kampong R, Pompimon W, Meepowpan P, Sukdee S, Sombutsiri P, Nantasaen N, et al. (-)-7-O-acetylgoniodiol as cancer chemopreventive agent from *Goniothalamus Griffithii*. *Int J Chem Sci* 2013;11:1234–46.
 18. Palani V, Chinnaraj S, Shanmugasundaram M, Malaisamy A, Maluventhen V, Arumugam VA, et al. Derivation, Functionalization of (S)-Goniothalamine from *Goniothalamus wightii* and Their Derivative Targets SARS-CoV-2 MPro, SPro, and RdRp: A Pharmacological Perspective. *Molecules* 2022;27(20):6962.
 19. Khan R, Ahmed N, Chowdhury A, Keya S, Runa M, Munni MN, et al. Phytochemical screening of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis*. *J Med Plants Stud [Internet]* 2018 [cited 2024 Jan 8]; Available from: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Phytochemical-screening-of-Goniothalamus-Khan-Ahmed/dcf2e254ca2784761d6b4f3f87c35b9ef892e54f>
 20. Konsam SC, Ningthoujam SS, Potsangbam KS. Antibacterial Activity and Phytochemical Screening of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* (Wall.) Hook. f. & Thomson Extracts from Manipur, North East India. *Eur J Med Plants* 2015;142–8.
 21. Sharma M, Chopra C, Mehta M, Sharma V, Mallubhotla S, Sistla S, et al. An Insight into Vaginal Microbiome Techniques. *Life* 2021;11(11):1229.
 22. Shahzad Aslam M, Syarhabil Ahmad M, Soh Mamat A, et al. *Goniothalamus*: Phytochemical and Ethnobotanical Review. *Recent Adv Biol Med* 2016;02:34.
 23. Brée B, Helmstetter AJ, Bethune K, Ghogue JP, Sonké B, Couvreur TLP. Diversification of African Rainforest Restricted Clades: Piptostigmataceae and Annickieae (Annonaceae). *Diversity* 2020;12(6):227.
 24. Couvreur TLP, Helmstetter AJ, Koenen EJM, Bethune K, Brandão RD, Little SA, et al.

- Phylogenomics of the Major Tropical Plant Family Annonaceae Using Targeted Enrichment of Nuclear Genes. *Front Plant Sci* [Internet] 2019 [cited 2024 Jun 4];9. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/plant-science/articles/10.3389/fpls.2018.01941/full>
25. Talapatra SK, Basu D, Chattopadhyay P, Talapatra B. Aristololactams of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* wall. Revised structures of the 2-oxygenated aristololactams. *Phytochemistry* 1988;27(3):903–6.
26. Hasan CM, Mia MY, Rashid MA, Connolly JD. 5-acetoxyisogoniothalamine oxide, an epoxystryryl lactone from *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis*. *Phytochemistry* 1994;37(6):1763–4.
27. Guan L, Yang H, Cai Y, Sun L, Di P, Li W, et al. ADMET-score – a comprehensive scoring function for evaluation of chemical drug-likeness †Electronic supplementary information (ESI) available. See DOI: 10.1039/c8md00472b. *MedChemComm* 2018;10(1):148–57.
28. Xiong G, Wu Z, Yi J, Fu L, Yang Z, Hsieh C, et al. ADMETlab 2.0: an integrated online platform for accurate and comprehensive predictions of ADMET properties. *Nucleic Acids Res* 2021;49(W1):W5–14.
29. George V, T P I, Sreedevi P, Anzar S, Bincy A, Rajasekharan S, et al. Ethnobiology, ethnobotanist, ethnomedicine and traditional knowledge with special reference to India. *Ann Phytomedicine* 2013;2:4–12.
30. Raikwar A, Maurya P. ETHNOVETERINARY MEDICINE: IN PRESENT PERSPECTIVE [Internet]. 2015 [cited 2024 Jun 2]. Available from: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/ETHNOVETERINARY-MEDICINE%3A-IN-PRESENT-PERSPECTIVE-Raikwar-Maurya/61d582efe5ad3f5e0696bc3f0d9ac5a1ec43030a>
31. Singh YD, Panda MK, Satapathy KB. Ethnomedicine for Drug Discovery [Internet]. In: Patra JK, Shukla AC, Das G, editors. *Advances in Pharmaceutical Biotechnology: Recent Progress and Future Applications*. Singapore: Springer; 2020 [cited 2024 Jun 1]. page 15–28. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-2195-9_2
32. Gurmet P. “Sowa - Rigpa” : Himalayan art of healing. *IJTK Vol32 April 2004* [Internet] 2004 [cited 2024 Jun 2]; Available from: <http://nopr.niscpr.res.in/handle/123456789/345>
33. Kapur M. Gleanings from Siddha Medicine [Internet]. In: *Psychological Perspectives on Childcare in Indian Indigenous Health Systems*. New Delhi: Springer India; 2016 [cited 2024 Jun 2]. page 215–21. Available from: https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-81-322-2428-0_19
34. Mukherjee A, Banerjee M, Mandal V, Shukla AC, Mandal SC. Modernization of Ayurveda: A Brief Overview of Indian Initiatives. *Nat Prod Commun* 2014;9(2):1934578X1400900.
35. Prakash BN, Hariramamurthi G, Sarin NS, Unnikrishnan PM. Strengthening Capacity of Tribal Communities to Revitalise Tribal Medicine Through Research, Education and Outreach [Internet]. In: Reddy S, Guite N, Subedi B, editors. *Ethnomedicine and Tribal Healing Practices in India*. Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore; 2023 [cited 2024 Jun 1]. page 277–85. Available from: https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-981-19-4286-0_18
36. Weiner MA. Ethnomedicine in Tonga. *Econ Bot* 1971;25(4):423–50.
37. Shakri NM, Salleh WMNH, Shaharudin SM. Review on Malaysian *Goniothalamus*

- essential oils and their comparative study using multivariate statistical analysis. *Nat Volatiles Essent Oils* 2021;8(1):1–12.
38. Adhya I, Pudji Widodo, Cecep Kusmana, Eming Sudiana, Imam Widhiono, Toto Supartono. Short Communication: Population structure and habitat characteristics of *Goniothalamus macrophyllus* in Bukit Pembarisan forest, West Java, Indonesia. *Biodiversitas J Biol Divers* [Internet] 2020 [cited 2024 Jun 3];21(3). Available from: <https://smujo.id/biodiv/article/view/5224>
39. CABI. *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2024 May 13];25648. Available from: <http://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/10.1079/cabicompendium.25648>
40. Leeratiwong C, Chalermglin P, Saunders RMK. *Goniothalamus roseipetalus* and *G. sukhirinensis* (Annonaceae): Two new species from Peninsular Thailand. *PhytoKeys* 2021;184:1–17.
41. Hayhoe EJ, Palombo EA. Screening for Antibacterial, Antifungal, and Anti quorum Sensing Activity [Internet]. In: Roessner U, Dias DA, editors. *Metabolomics Tools for Natural Product Discovery*. Totowa, NJ: Humana Press; 2013 [cited 2024 Jun 3]. page 219–25. Available from: https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-1-62703-577-4_16
42. Rahman F. Study of antioxidant and antimicrobial activity of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* in ethanol extract. *J Med Plants Stud* [Internet] 2019 [cited 2024 Jun 1]; Available from: https://www.academia.edu/82565359/Study_of_antioxidant_and_antimicrobial_activity_of_Goniothalamus_sesquipedalis_in_ethanol_extract
43. Habiba NA, Akter N, Ferdushi M, Afrin T, Munni MN, Akter M. Investigation of Anthelmintic and Insecticidal activity of *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis* plant in different extracts. *J Med Plants Stud* 2019;7(2):30–4.
44. Bhargav HS, Shastri SD, Poornav SP, Darshan KM, Nayak MM. Measurement of the Zone of Inhibition of an Antibiotic [Internet]. In: 2016 IEEE 6th International Conference on Advanced Computing (IACC). Bhimavaram, India: IEEE; 2016 [cited 2024 Jun 3]. page 409–14. Available from: <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7544871/>
45. Delignette-Muller ML, Flandrois JP. An accurate diffusion method for determining bacterial sensitivity to antibiotics. *J Antimicrob Chemother* 1994;34(1):73–81.
46. Saikkonen K, Nissinen R, Helander M. Toward Comprehensive Plant Microbiome Research. *Front Ecol Evol* 2020;8:61.
47. Brocks JJ, Hope JM. Tailing of Chromatographic Peaks in GC–MS Caused by Interaction of Halogenated Solvents with the Ion Source. *J Chromatogr Sci* 2014;52(6):471–5.
48. Chung HH, Kao CY, Wang TSA, Chu J, Pei J, Hsu CC. Reaction Tracking and High-Throughput Screening of Active Compounds in Combinatorial Chemistry by Tandem Mass Spectrometry Molecular Networking. *Anal Chem* 2021;93(4):2456–63.
49. Noriega P, Gortaire G, Osorio E. Mass Spectrometry and Its Importance for the Analysis and Discovery of Active Molecules in Natural Products [Internet]. In: A. El-Shemy H, editor. *Natural Drugs from Plants*. IntechOpen; 2022 [cited 2024 Jun 4]. Available from: <https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/76771>
50. Witkowski S, Wawer I. NMR Spectroscopy in Drug and Natural Product Analysis [Internet]. In: Andrushko V, Andrushko N, editors. *Stereoselective Synthesis of Drugs and*

- Natural Products. Wiley; 2013 [cited 2024 Jun 4]. page 1–24. Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/9781118596784.ssd049>
51. Arshad M. Heterocyclic compounds bearing pyrimidine, oxazole and pyrazole moieties: design, computational, synthesis, characterization, antibacterial and molecular docking screening. *SN Appl Sci* 2020;2(3):467.
52. Fahim AM, Tolan HEM, Awad H, Ismael EHI. Synthesis, antimicrobial and antiproliferative activities, molecular docking, and computational studies of novel heterocycles. *J Iran Chem Soc* 2021;18(11):2965–81.
53. Hariprasath B. Molecular docking studies of plant derived compounds. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res* 2012;5:87–8.
54. Sahu SN, Moharana M, Sahu R, Pattanayak SK. Molecular docking approach study of binding performance of antifungal proteins [Internet]. Bahal, India: 2019 [cited 2024 Jun 4]. page 060001. Available from: <https://pubs.aip.org/aip/acp/article/725331>
55. Temml V, Schuster D. Molecular Docking for Natural Product Investigations: Pitfalls and Ways to Overcome Them [Internet]. In: *Molecular Docking for Computer-Aided Drug Design*. Elsevier; 2021 [cited 2024 Jun 4]. page 391–405. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/B9780128223123000278>
56. Mustafa G, Mehmood R, Mahrosh HS, Mehmood K, Ahmed S. Investigation of Plant Antimicrobial Peptides against Selected Pathogenic Bacterial Species Using a Peptide-Protein Docking Approach. *BioMed Res Int* 2022;2022:1–11.
57. Qian M, Ismail BB, He Q, Zhang X, Yang Z, Ding T, et al. Inhibitory mechanisms of promising antimicrobials from plant byproducts: A review. *Compr Rev Food Sci Food Saf* 2023;22(4):2523–90.
58. Azad I. Molecular Docking in the Study of Ligand-Protein Recognition: An Overview [Internet]. In: Salih Istifli E, editor. *Biomedical Engineering*. IntechOpen; 2023 [cited 2024 Jun 4]. Available from: <https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/83584>
59. Dnyandev KM, Babasaheb GV, Chandrashekhar KV, Chandrakant MA, Vasant OK. A Review on Molecular Docking. *Int Res J Pure Appl Chem* 2021;60–8.
60. Jaiswal C, Pant KK, Behera RKS, Bhatt R, Chandra V. Development of New Molecules Through Molecular Docking [Internet]. In: Verma P, editor. *Industrial Microbiology and Biotechnology*. Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore; 2023 [cited 2024 Jun 4]. page 643–60. Available from: https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-981-99-2816-3_22
61. Saikia S, Puzari M, Chetia P. Molecular Docking in Drug Designing and Metabolism [Internet]. In: Verma P, editor. *Industrial Microbiology and Biotechnology*. Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore; 2023 [cited 2024 May 28]. page 403–30. Available from: https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-981-99-2816-3_14
62. Srivastava N, Garg P, Singh A, Srivastava P. Chapter Three - Molecular docking approaches and its significance in assessing the antioxidant properties in different compounds [Internet]. In: Litwack G, editor. *Vitamins and Hormones*. Academic Press; 2023 [cited 2024 May 28]. page 67–80. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0083672922000747>
63. Jian JY, McCarty KD, Byl JAW, Guengerich FP, Neuman KC, Osheroff N. Basis for the discrimination of supercoil handedness during

- DNA cleavage by human and bacterial type II topoisomerases. *Nucleic Acids Res* 2023;51(8):3888–902.
64. Martínez-García B, Valdés A, Segura J, Dyson S, Díaz-Ingelmo O, Roca J. Electrophoretic Analysis of the DNA Supercoiling Activity of DNA Gyrase [Internet]. In: Lavelle C, editor. *Molecular Motors*. New York, NY: Springer New York; 2018 [cited 2024 Jun 4]. page 291–300. Available from: http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-1-4939-8556-2_15
65. Villain P, Catchpole R, Forterre P, Oberto J, Da Cunha V, Basta T. Expanded Dataset Reveals the Emergence and Evolution of DNA Gyrase in Archaea. *Mol Biol Evol* 2022;39(8):msac155.
66. Adewumi AT, Oluyemi WM, Adekunle YA, Adewumi N, Alahmdi MI, Soliman MES, et al. Propitious Indazole Compounds as β -ketoacyl-ACP Synthase Inhibitors and Mechanisms Unfolded for TB Cure: Integrated Rational Design and MD Simulations. *ChemistrySelect* 2023;8(3):e202203877.
67. Chen A, Mindrebo JT, Davis TD, Kim WE, Katsuyama Y, Jiang Z, et al. Mechanism-based crosslinking probes capture *E. coli* ketosynthase FabB in conformationally-distinct catalytic states [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2024 Jun 4]; Available from: <http://biorxiv.org/lookup/doi/10.1101/2022.04.04.486996>
68. Yu YH, Chen C, Ma JR, Zhang YY, Yan MF, Zhang WB, et al. The FabA-FabB Pathway Is Not Essential for Unsaturated Fatty Acid Synthesis but Modulates Diffusible Signal Factor Synthesis in *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *campestris*. *Mol Plant-Microbe Interactions®* 2023;36(2):119–30.
69. Sama-ae I, Pattarangoon NC, Tedasen A. In silico prediction of Antifungal compounds from Natural sources towards Lanosterol 14-alpha demethylase (CYP51) using Molecular docking and Molecular dynamic simulation. *J Mol Graph Model* 2023;121:108435.
70. Singh A, Singh K, Sharma A, Kaur K, Chadha R, Bedi PMS. Recent advances in antifungal drug development targeting lanosterol 14 α -demethylase (CYP51): A comprehensive review with structural and molecular insights. *Chem Biol Drug Des* 2023;102(3):606–39.
71. Murphy SG, Murtha AN, Zhao Z, Alvarez L, Diebold P, Shin JH, et al. Class A Penicillin-Binding Protein-mediated cell wall synthesis promotes structural integrity during peptidoglycan endopeptidase insufficiency [Internet]. 2020 [cited 2024 Jun 4]; Available from: <http://biorxiv.org/lookup/doi/10.1101/2020.07.03.187153>
72. Straume D, Piechowiak KW, Olsen S, Stamsås GA, Berg KH, Kjos M, et al. Class A PBPs have a distinct and unique role in the construction of the pneumococcal cell wall. *Proc Natl Acad Sci* 2020;117(11):6129–38.
73. Wacnik K, Rao VA, Chen X, Lafage L, Pazos M, Booth S, et al. PBP1 of *Staphylococcus aureus* has multiple essential functions in cell division [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2024 Jun 4]; Available from: <http://biorxiv.org/lookup/doi/10.1101/2021.10.07.463504>
74. Zhang H, Venkatesan S, Ng E, Nan B. The coordination between penicillin-binding protein 1a (PBP1a) and the hydrolytic peptidase DacB determines the integrity of bacterial cell poles [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2024 Jun 4]; Available from: <http://biorxiv.org/lookup/doi/10.1101/2022.03.18.484884>

75. Hussein A, Gamal R, Refaat A, Abdel-Salam A, Ramadan K. Synergistic Effect Of Some Plant Extracts And Antibiotic Drugs Against Staph. Aureus Isolated From Pleural Fluid Identification Of The Active Compounds. *Arab Univ J Agric Sci* 2017;25(2):387–401.
76. Mehta J, Jandaik S, . U. Evaluation Of Phytochemicals And Synergistic Interaction Between Plant Extracts And Antibiotics For Efflux Pump Inhibitory Activity Against Salmonella Enterica Serovar Typhimurium Strains. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci* 2016;8(10):217.
77. Alam MdN, Bristi NJ, Rafiquzzaman Md. Review on in vivo and in vitro methods evaluation of antioxidant activity. *Saudi Pharm J* 2013;21(2):143–52.
78. Gulcin İ, Alwaseel SH. DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay. *Processes* 2023;11(8):2248.
79. Munteanu IG, Apetrei C. Analytical Methods Used in Determining Antioxidant Activity: A Review. *Int J Mol Sci* 2021;22(7):3380.
80. Pyrzynska K, Pękal A. Application of free radical diphenylpicrylhydrazyl (DPPH) to estimate the antioxidant capacity of food samples. *Anal Methods* 2013;5(17):4288.
81. Tatarczak-Michalewska M, Fliieger J. Application of High-Performance Liquid Chromatography with Diode Array Detection to Simultaneous Analysis of Reference Antioxidants and 1,1-Diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) in Free Radical Scavenging Test. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 2022;19(14):8288.
82. Yeo J, Shahidi F. Critical Re-Evaluation of DPPH assay: Presence of Pigments Affects the Results. *J Agric Food Chem* 2019;67(26):7526–9.
83. Celiz G, Renfige M, Finetti M. Spectral analysis allows using the DPPH* UV–Vis assay to estimate antioxidant activity of colored compounds. *Chem Pap* 2020;74(9):3101–9.
84. Abramovič H, Grobin B, Poklar Ulrich N, Cigić B. The Methodology Applied in DPPH, ABTS and Folin-Ciocalteu Assays Has a Large Influence on the Determined Antioxidant Potential. *Acta Chim Slov* 2017;64(2):491–9.
85. La J, Kim MJ, Lee J. Evaluation of solvent effects on the DPPH reactivity for determining the antioxidant activity in oil matrix. *Food Sci Biotechnol* 2021;30(3):367–75.
86. Xie J, Schaich KM. Re-evaluation of the 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl Free Radical (DPPH) Assay for Antioxidant Activity. *J Agric Food Chem* 2014;62(19):4251–60.
87. C Moreira D. ABTS decolorization assay – in vitro antioxidant capacity v1 [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2024 Jun 4]; Available from: <https://www.protocols.io/view/abts-decolorization-assay-in-vitro-antioxidant-cap-42xgyfn>
88. Kulkarni K, Govindaiah G. Evaluation of Anti-oxidant properties of some medicinal plant products by ABTS Radical Scavenging Assay. *Res J Sci Technol* 2022;213–8.
89. Matsumoto K, Taniarashi M, Tsutaho Y, Yamada A, Yosho A, Osakai T, et al. Redox reactions between ABTS•+ and dihydroxybenzenes as studied by cyclic voltammetry. *Anal Sci* 2022;38(1):227–30.
90. Benzie I, M D. The ferric reducing/antioxidant power (FRAP) assay for non-enzymatic antioxidant capacity: concepts, procedures, limitations and applications: Recent Trends and Applications. In: *Measurement of Antioxidant Activity and Capacity: Recent Trends and Applications*. 2017. page 77–106.
91. Nwachukwu ID, Sarteshnizi RA, Udenigwe CC, Aluko RE. A Concise Review of Current

- In Vitro Chemical and Cell-Based Antioxidant Assay Methods. *Molecules* 2021;26(16):4865.
92. Carvalho JRB, Meireles AN, Marques SS, Gregório BJR, Ramos II, Silva EMP, et al. Exploiting Kinetic Features of ORAC Assay for Evaluation of Radical Scavenging Capacity. *Antioxidants* 2023;12(2):505.
93. Villaruz J ar, Yao KB, Dela Cruz F, Calanasan C, Matias R, Pagcatipunan R, et al. Total Phenolic and Flavonoid Content and In Vitro Antioxidant Activity of Selected Herbal Products Using Oxygen Radical Absorbance Capacity, Multi-radical (ORAC MR5) Assays. *Philipp J Sci [Internet]* 2023 [cited 2024 Jun 4];152(1). Available from: <https://philjournalsci.dost.gov.ph/publication/regular-issues/past-issues/117-vol-152-no-1-february-2023/1803-total-phenolic-and-flavonoid-content-and-in-vitro-antioxidant-activity-of-selected-herbal-products-using-oxygen-radical-absorbance-capacity-multi-radical-orac-mr5-assays>
94. Chelliah R, Oh DH. Screening for Antioxidant Activity: Metal Chelating Assay [Internet]. In: Dharumadurai D, editor. *Methods in Actinobacteriology*. New York, NY: Springer US; 2022 [cited 2024 Jun 4]. page 457–8. Available from: https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-1-0716-1728-1_63
95. Josiah S, Boisclair M. High-throughput screening assays utilizing metal-chelate capture [Internet]. 2000 [cited 2024 Jun 4]; Available from: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US6146842A/en>
96. De Torre MP, Cavero RY, Calvo MI, Vizmanos JL. A Simple and a Reliable Method to Quantify Antioxidant Activity In Vivo. *Antioxidants* 2019;8(5):142.
97. Thangaraj P. In Vivo Antioxidant Assays [Internet]. In: *Pharmacological Assays of Plant-Based Natural Products*. Cham: Springer International Publishing; 2016 [cited 2024 Jun 4]. page 89–98. Available from: http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-319-26811-8_14
98. Hassanpour SH, Doroudi A. Review of the antioxidant potential of flavonoids as a subgroup of polyphenols and partial substitute for synthetic antioxidants. *Avicenna J Phytomedicine* 2023;13(4):354–76.
99. Macáková K, Afonso R, Saso L, Mladěnka P. The influence of alkaloids on oxidative stress and related signaling pathways. *Free Radic Biol Med* 2019;134:429–44.
100. Tong Z, He W, Fan X, Guo A. Biological Function of Plant Tannin and Its Application in Animal Health. *Front Vet Sci [Internet]* 2022 [cited 2024 Jun 4];8. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fvets.2021.803657>
101. Al-Khayri JM, Sahana GR, Nagella P, Joseph BV, Alessa FM, Al-Mssallem MQ. Flavonoids as Potential Anti-Inflammatory Molecules: A Review. *Molecules* 2022;27(9):2901.
102. Bai R, Yao C, Zhong Z, Ge J, Bai Z, Ye X, et al. Discovery of natural anti-inflammatory alkaloids: Potential leads for the drug discovery for the treatment of inflammation. *Eur J Med Chem* 2021;213:113165.
103. Bjørklund G, Shanaida M, Lysiuk R, Butnariu M, Peana M, Sarac I, et al. Natural Compounds and Products from an Anti-Aging Perspective. *Molecules* 2022;27(20):7084.
104. Çetinkaya S, Taban Akça K, Süntar I. Chapter 3 - Flavonoids and anticancer activity: Structure–activity relationship [Internet]. In: Atta-ur-Rahman, editor. *Studies*

- in Natural Products Chemistry. Elsevier; 2022 [cited 2024 Jun 4]. page 81–115. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780323910996000177>
105. Kleszcz R, Majchrzak-Celińska A, Baer-Dubowska W. Tannins in cancer prevention and therapy. *Br J Pharmacol* 2023;
106. Mondal A, Gandhi A, Fimognari C, Atanasov AG, Bishayee A. Alkaloids for cancer prevention and therapy: Current progress and future perspectives. *Eur J Pharmacol* 2019;858:172472.
107. Okoro NO, Odiba AS, Osadebe PO, Omeje EO, Liao G, Fang W, et al. Bioactive Phytochemicals with Anti-Aging and Lifespan Extending Potentials in *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Molecules* 2021;26(23):7323.
108. Sangrueng K, Sanyacharernkul S, Nantapap S, Nantasaen N, Pompimon W. Bioactive Goniothalamine from *Goniothalamus tapis* with Cytotoxic Potential. *Am J Appl Sci* 2015;12(9):650–3.
109. Choo CY, Abdullah N, Diederich M. Cytotoxic activity and mechanism of action of metabolites from the *Goniothalamus* genus. *Phytochem Rev* 2014;13(4):835–51.
110. Yaws CL, Narasimhan PK, Lou HH, Pike RW. Solubility of Chemicals in Water [Internet]. In: Lehr JH, Keeley J, editors. *Water Encyclopedia*. Wiley; 2004 [cited 2024 Jun 4]. page 555–9. Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/047147844X.pc1605>
111. Soares JX, Santos Á, Fernandes C, Pinto MMM. Liquid Chromatography on the Different Methods for the Determination of Lipophilicity: An Essential Analytical Tool in Medicinal Chemistry. *Chemosensors* 2022;10(8):340.
112. Wardecki D, Dołowy M, Bober-Majnuś K. Assessment of Lipophilicity Parameters of Antimicrobial and Immunosuppressive Compounds. *Molecules* 2023;28(6):2820.
113. Dubey A, Patel BA, Parmar SJ. Combined novel approach to enhance the solubility and Intestinal absorption: A recent review. *EJPPS Eur J Parenter Pharm Sci* [Internet] 2023 [cited 2024 Jun 4]; Available from: <https://www.ejpps.online/post/vol28-1-combined-novel-approach-to-enhance-the-solubility-and-intestinal-absorption>
114. Shokry DS, Waters LJ, Parkes GMB, Mitchell JC. Prediction of human intestinal absorption using micellar liquid chromatography with an aminopropyl stationary phase. *Biomed Chromatogr* 2019;33(7):e4515.
115. Cornelissen FMG, Markert G, Deutsch G, Antonara M, Faaij N, Bartelink I, et al. Explaining Blood–Brain Barrier Permeability of Small Molecules by Integrated Analysis of Different Transport Mechanisms. *J Med Chem* 2023;66(11):7253–67.
116. Wanat K, Brzezińska E. Chromatographic Data in Statistical Analysis of BBB Permeability Indices. *Membranes* 2023;13(7):623.
117. Ahmed H, Bergmann F, Zeitlinger M. Protein Binding in Translational Antimicrobial Development-Focus on Interspecies Differences. *Antibiotics* 2022;11(7):923.
118. Khaouane A, Ferhat S, Hanini S. A Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship for Human Plasma Protein Binding: Prediction, Validation and Applicability Domain. *Adv Pharm Bull* 2023;13(4):784–91.

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